

The Design of Decorative Flower Patterns from Suansunandha Palace

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II. OBJECTIVES

- 1) To investigate flowers grown in Suansunandha Palace as a source of motif design.
- 2) To design motifs inspired by flowers grown in Suansunandha Palace.
- 3) To a creative design from the flower motifs to be applied in souvenirs design.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Population of Study

The population in this study is the products that use pattern design for value creation. There are photo frames, wrapping paper and gift boxes.

B. Research Tools

- 1) The photographs of flowers in water color paints by ladies in waiting of Her Royal Highness Prince Saisawarepirom as the source for investigating flowers in Suansunandha Palace.
- 2) Pictures of real flowers grown in Suansunandha Palace.
- 3) Adobe Photoshop Program for designing motifs and decorative patterns including prototypes.

C. Research Procedure

- 1) The researcher studied the documents about types of plants and flowers which have been planted in Suansunandha Palace. The researcher found that there were many large trees, including padauk, fig, peacock flowers, asoka, etc. However, the cost of tree planty is unknown has Suansunandha Palace was part of Suandusit Palace. The cost of tree plant in the area was included in cost of palace construction [2].

In 2467 BE, the Princess had diabetes and stayed with her son, Prince Lopburiramet, at Laddawan Palace which is now the office of Crown Property Bureau. During that time, the Princess enjoyed gardening very much. After she came back to the royal palace, she found that there was not enough area for gardens, so she asked for permission from King Rama VI to stay at Suansunandha Palace. There, the Princess planted hundreds of roses in front of her palace with an orchid greenhouse and a lotus pond at the rear. Every morning Amorn, Sangium, Seng and other ladies-in-waiting of the Princess were assigned to paint flowers with watercolor in realistic style. [3]

In 2475 BE, Thai political system had changed from the Absolute Monarchy to Democracy. All the royal family members evacuated and left the Suansunandha Palace. During the reign of King Rama VIII, the cabinet agreed to harden the

Abstract—The study on the design of decorative flower patterns from Suansunandha Palace is a innovative design using flowers grown in Suansunandha Palace as the original sources. The research tools included: 1) The photographs of flowers in water colors painted by one of the ladies in waiting of Her Royal Highness Princess Saisawarepirom as the source for investigating flowers grown in Suansunandha Palace 2) Pictures of real flowers grown in Suansunandha Palace 3) Adobe Illustrator Program and Adobe Photoshop Program in designing motifs and decorative patterns including prototypes. The researcher chose 3 types of Suansunandha Palace's flowers; moss roses, orchids, and lignum vitae. The details of the flowers were simplified to create motifs for more elaborate decorative patterns. There were 4 motifs adapted from moss roses, 3 motifs adapted from orchids, and 3 motifs adapted from lignum vitae. The patterns were used to decorate photo frames, wrapping paper, and gift boxes or souvenir boxes.

Keywords—Suansunandha Palace, decoration design, floral pattern.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the creation of any artwork, one important component enhancing the beauty of the artwork is the decorative pattern. Pattern design can enrich decorations. Decorative patterns are used in several types of work including architecture, artwork, sculpture, hand crafts, etc. Generally, decorative patterns are design from nature, such as plants and animals.

Suansunandha Palace, a royal premise in the past, was founded by King Rama V. This area used to be a garden full with a variety of rare plants, flowers, and fruits. At the backyard of Her Royal Highness Princess Saisawarepirom's palace, there was a big pond with a variety of lotuses. H.R.H. was very fond of trees and flowers, so, her palace was surrounded with big trees and fragrant flowers. Each morning one of her ladies in waiting had to paint a flower in the garden for her. Her favorite flowers were frangipani, orchids, and roses. H.R.H. spent a lot of money on buying trees and flowers such as to be grown and other around her palace rare flowers [1]. The researcher chose to use the flowers grown in the palace as a source of inspiration for designing decorative patterns.

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palace to the Ministry of Education to establish a public school called "Suan Sunandha Collage". Late the college became teacher college. [4]

Fig. 1 Watercolor painting of moss roses in a vase

Fig. 2 Watercolor painting of moss roses

Fig. 3 The photo of Lignum Vitae [5]

Fig. 4 Watercolor painting of orchids

- 2) The researcher studied pattern design found that the most important part of pattern design is motifs. Motifs could be anything in simple style which can be easily developed to patterns. [6]
- 3) The researcher chose 3 types of Suansunandha Palace flowers; moss roses, orchids, and lignum vitae. The details of the flowers were simplified to create motifs for elaborative decoration. There were 4 motifs adapted from moss roses, 3 motifs adapted from orchids, and 3 motifs adapted from Lignum Vitae.

Fig. 5 Motifs from moss roses 1

Fig. 6 Motifs from moss roses 2

Fig. 7 Motifs from moss roses 3

Fig. 8 Motifs from moss roses 4

Fig. 9 Orchids, Motifs 1

Fig. 10 Orchids, Motifs 2

Fig. 11 Orchids, Motifs 3

Fig. 12 Motifs from Lignum Vitae 1

Fig. 13 Motifs from Lignum Vitae 2

Fig. 14 Motifs from Lignum Vitae 3

- 4) Three motifs of moss roses were designed by extending but the flipped motifs with image rotation circular shape, brick together and half drop network. This type of design is used with the limited area or circular areas.

Fig. 15 Moss rose, pattern 1

Fig. 16 Moss rose, pattern 2

- 5) Three motifs from orchids were developed into 3 edging patterns: border line, diamond shape and square shape.

Fig. 17 Orchid pattern in border design

Fig. 18 Orchid pattern in diamond shape design

Fig. 19 Orchid pattern in square shape design

- 6) Three motifs from Lignum Vitae were developed into a square shape, the edging pattern, and a vertical pattern.

Fig. 20 Lignum Vitae pattern in square design

Fig. 21 Lignum Vitae pattern in border design

Fig. 22 Lignum Vitae pattern in vertical pattern

7) The patterns were used to decorate types products of 3.

Fig. 23 Photo frame of 6X8 inches and 8X10 inches at the border pattern

8) Three types of wrapping paper with the design of the brick-and-half-drop network pattern, the vertical network pattern, and the diamond network pattern.

Fig. 24 Three types of wrapping paper with the design of the brick-and-half-drop network pattern, the vertical network pattern, and the diamond Network pattern

9) Gift boxes or souvenir boxes were decorated by 3 designs of check pattern, square pattern, and vertical pattern.

Fig. 25 Gift boxes or souvenir boxes decorated by 3 designs of the brick and half-drop network pattern and the square network pattern

Fig. 26 Gift box decorated by the vertical network pattern

IV. RESULT

The researcher selected 3 types of flowers to design motif moss roses, orchids, and Lignum Vitae. The research simplified the details of each flower while maintaining the identity of each flower.

- 1) The researcher designed 4 motifs of moss roses and 2 patterns of moss roses decorative patterns. The technique employed in the design was image reflection, rotation and transition. Other designs included the brick-and-half-drop network pattern with the sign of letter “a” under the crown. Due to more details, the color should be beige or white to enhance the pattern.
- 2) There are many types of orchids in the palace. The researcher chose to design 3 motifs from orchids which were the motif of the flower, the motif of flowers and leaves, and the motif with added decoration. The motifs can be developed to other types such as square pattern, diamond shape, and etc. The color should be white and the background color should be light color.
- 3) Lignum Vitae is very important because King Rama V, imported it and planted in SuanSunandha Palace for the first time. The researcher designed 3 motifs in the form of square pattern, border pattern, and vertical pattern.

The pattern design in this study could be applied to other products:

Fig. 23: Photo frame was used border design pattern to decorate the photo frame.

Fig. 24: Wrapping paper, the pattern can be extended or adjusted due to the size of the products.

Figs. 25-26: Gift box or Souvenir box design pattern can be used to decorate the ordinary box into more stylish and more elaborative boxes.

V. CONCLUSION

- 1) There are many types are an inspiration from Suansunandha Palace which can be used for designing new motifs.
- 2) There are many techniques for designing motif. Apart from cutting off the details, other techniques include drawing and fusion technique.
- 3) In designing decorative pattern, motif design is very important as motifs are the heart of decorative patterns.

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